

PERCEIVED PUBLIC IMAGE AND ITS INFLUENCE ON NURSING CAREER TURNOVER INTENTION AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS AT KING ABDUL-AZIZ UNIVERSITY, SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract

Background: The stereotypical public image of nursing is a major concern to nursing. However, it is relatively unknown how this image effects on turnover intention of students. A few studies investigate impact of perception of public image of nursing on turnover intention of student from nursing professional as mentioned by (1) many of the Saudi literature, they cited main negative images of nursing and perceived low status of nurses as two important factors in explaining the severe shortage of Saudi nurses. These factors as gender-mixing, long working hours and rotating shifts which make nursing a socially unacceptable occupational choice. AIM: This study aimed to explore the impact of public image on turnover intention of female students from joining to nursing profession at king Abdul-Aziz University. METHOD: A convenience sample of 100 Saudi female students king Abdul-Aziz University and 90 their parents were collected. This descriptive correlation study was performed and data was analyzed with t-test. RESULTS: revealed that 87.8% of the parents were disagreeing with teaching one of my sons nursing. CONCLUSION: To reduce turnover intention of student it is important improving the public image of nursing and student image.

Keywords: image, public image, nursing image

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite the great advances in the nursing profession, nurses still face considerable challenges related to its image that impact on status, power and the ability to affect changes in health care. Where, a negative image of nursing has a number of negative consequences, it has impacts on the quality and quantity of persons who choose nursing as a profession. The public who are constantly presented with an inaccurate and negative nursing image will view a career in nursing as undesirable. This is especially relevant to the recruitment of men in the field where media portrayals have focused primarily on women while the image of a male nurse is often negative (2). As well as (3) stated that ever feeling a person has about him/herself as a professional will affect his/her way of thought and action in professional relations. Therefore nurses, who have positive professional images, will have more and stronger remedial relations with their parents in addition to (4) found that both doctors and the public have a negative image about nursing as a profession. Doctors see nurses as their handmaiden and therefore negative image of nursing continues to be a problem. Nurses are professionals who are science driven, technically skilled, and caring. Many people still perceived that nursing is not good enough for high modern class women. And of course, a nursing job

with that image will not attract for many men either. **So** nursing has traditionally been perceived as more appropriate work for women, because women are inherently maternal, feminine and nurturing, also reflecting the traditional gender roles of women as gentle, submissive, self-effacing, and self-sacrificing by nature (5;6). Many of societies and its media still regard nursing as women's work that is not appropriate for men. Even the English language reflects this idea. The terms "matron" and "ward sister" remain common in some nations. And many people wrongly believe that men become nurses only if they're not intelligent enough to be physicians. The stereotypical public image of nursing is a major concern to nurses. However, it is relatively unknown how this image affects nurses. A few studies have investigated how nurses' interpretations of their public image affect their self-image and work behavior (7). While added by (8) poor public understanding of the profession underlies many of the more immediate causes of the global nursing shortage. Written by (9), developing nursing work-force shortage, expected to peak in the next 10 years. In order to recruit the clever and intelligent students into nursing, it is important that students, teachers, psychotherapy and social worker have a more objective view of the role of a nurse. The traditional view, focused on the qualities of nurses as caring, kindly workers, does not accurately portray the academic rigor required to become a nurse. These ideas hamper nursing recruitment, retention, and practice. Many of immediate causes of nursing crises have their roots in undervaluation of their profession which is driven by stereotypes and mass media plays a key role informing and reinforcing.

II. Subjects And Methods

Design

The present study is a descriptive exploratory study aiming to explore the impact of public image on turnover intention of female students from joining to nursing profession at king Abdul -Aziz University

Setting:

This study was carried out in King Abdul- Aziz University- as well as public in Jeddah city in kingdom Saudi Arabia.

Subjects:

The subjects of this study consisted of a selected numbers of students from King Abdul Aziz University. They were 190 studied sample divided into 100 students from different colleges at female campus and divided as 90 from public.

Tools of Data Collection:

Data was collected by using two main modified tools from; (10 ;11), this tool aimed to explore Impact of public image on turnover intention of students from nursing profession at king Abdul -Aziz University in Jeddah. Tool for data collection was a questionnaire composed of six parts. The first part of the questionnaire was developed by the researchers to collect data related to demographic characteristics of studied students as their age, faculty name; income level, number of family. Second part namely: attitudes which influence the image of nursing: It includes 24 questions related to student's image regarding nursing profession. Third part: Identify the effect of turnover students on the nursing profession 10 questions

related to effect of turnover students on the nursing profession. Final part: open ended question related to suggestions to improve nursing image. The same tool was used for public after modification was done

III. Methods of Data collection:

Pilot Study:

Pilot study was carried out after the development of the tools on 10% of the students and 10 % of public to test applicability of the tools then necessary modification were done according to the results of the results of pilot study and expertise opinions. The purpose of pilot study was: To test the applicability of the study tools and to estimate any need for addition in the tool. Otherwise, the ten students and public were then excluded from the sample of research work to assure the stability of answers

Ethical Consideration:

Oral consents were obtained from the selected students and public as well as explain the aim of the study to each student's to be familiar with the importance of their participation and a brief explanation of the purpose and importance of the study was given to the student's and assured that the obtained information will be confidential and used only the purpose of the study. Confidentiality of the information was assured by the researcher.

Scoring system:

Scoring system for the responses was as follows: 1= yes and 2= no and 3=strongly agree, 2= agree and 1 = disagree. For each area, the scores of the items were summed and the total was divided by the number of the items, giving a mean score. These scores were then converted into percent score.

Data analysis:

Data was collected and entered into a database file. Statistical analysis was performed by using the SPSS 16 computer software statistical package. Data was described by summary tables and figures. For comparing the (Knowledge and attitude) with socio-demographic characteristics, T-test or Fisher Exact test was used. Statistical significance was considered at P-value <0.05 and highly significance at P-value <0.01.20% of the expected cell have count less than 5).

IV. Results

Table I shows sociodemographic characteristics of the studied subjects. Studied sample included in this study were 190, 100 from King Abdul-Aziz University and 90 from their parents. The majority of student's age ranged from 22 to 25 years, and there are a statistically significance difference between student's age group at p (0.000). While 8.4% of students from college of medicine female comps with income ranged between 10000-15000 RS and minor of them ranges from 5000 to 10000 RS and there are a statistically significance difference between student's income and type of colleges at p. (0.000).

Regarding to sociodemographic characteristics of parents the results indicated that most of parents' age ranged from 40 to 50 years, and above slightly half of them have children ranged from 1- 4 child. While 33.5% have tertiary school with low income ranged from 5000 to 10000 RS. Major percent of parents (22.5%) respectively working in different settings as governorate and private while the minor present among them 2.1% were not working and there are a statistically significance difference at p. (0.000).

Concerning comparison between the attitude towards the nursing profession between both students and parents. Table (3) recorded not agree 93.0%, 92.2%, and 82 %, respectively regarding to nursing profession in items; are you having any of your family nurse; are you having any of your relative/friends nurse; and are you agreeing for study nursing. While two third studied samples (74.4%) agree with item are you agreeing for study nursing?

Table (4): shows that there were a highly statistically difference between students and their parents in regarding aspects of nursing image in items; when I see a nurse I hope that my son or daughter works like; nursing profession humanitarian, work in the field of nursing is fit to a certain class of society and the presence of large numbers of foreign workers in the nursing profession dangers to society in the long run. While there is no statistically difference them regarding other aspects of nursing image.

Table (5): shows Comparison between Students and Parents opinion regarding the effects of the reluctance of the Saudi youth for the nursing Profession. Findings revealed that highest percent for studied sample (98%, 81.1%) respectively expressed agreement related to items: increase the level of employment among members of the community and weak of national security. Further the lowest percentage of strongly agreement was expressed by students and their parents were (7.0%) regarding items: dependence on foreign labor; bringing customs contrary to the habits of the Saudi society. There is no one was disagreed that there is increase the level of employment among members of the community followed by weak of national security

Table (6): present parents opinion regarding intend to teach female and male children in the field of nursing. Findings revealed that 87.8% of the parents were disagree with teaching one of my sons nursing

As **table (7):** there was highly significant differences between family income for both students and parents and study in the field of nursing. at $p = 0.0000^{***}$

According to **table (8):** there was highly significant difference between Students and their parents opinion regarding studying in the field of nursing in relation to their age where $P = 0.0000^{***}$

As showed in **table (9):** there was highly percentage (63) reported by students in relation to improve nurse's portrayal by media while low percent was 11% related to nurses should be training about communication skills especially with patients. Their parents reported highest percent (45) for continuous staff development while their opinion was low percent 11% for item Awareness for patients and their relatives about the nurse role.

TABLES

TABLE (1): SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS.

Characteristics	N= 100	%	X ²
Students Age			
19-22	36	18.8	0.002*
22-25	46	24.1	

Above 25	18	9.4	
College Types			
Pharmacist	14	7.3	0.380
Rehabilitation	13	6.8	
Laboratory	14	7.3	
Medicine	16	8.4	
Radiology	14	7.3	
Nutritionist	14	7.3	
Dentists	15	7.9	
Student's Income			
5-10000			0.000***
10000-15000	7	3.7	
Above 15000			

Table (2): Sociodemographic Characteristics of Parents.

Characteristics	N=	%	X ²
	90		
Parents Age			0.000***
40-45	42	22	
45-50	42	22	
Above 50	6	3.1	
Number of Children			
1-4 Child	58	30.4	
Above 4	32	16.8	
Parents Educations:			0.000***
Before Tertiary	5	2.6	
Tertiary	64	33.5	
High	19	9.9	
Postgraduate	2	1	
Parents Income:			
5-10000	67	35.1	
10000-15000	15	7.9	
Above 15000	8	4.2	
Occupation			0.000***
Governmental Employee	43	22.5	

Private Employee	43	22.5	
Not Working	4	2.1	

Table (3): Comparison between the attitude towards the Nursing Profession Between both Students and their Parents.

Group	Title	Opinion	N	%	Mean	SD
Student's	Are you having any of your family nurse?	Yes	18	18	1.8200	0.3816
		No	82	82		
Parent's	Are you having any of your family nurses?	Yes	7	7.8	1.9222	0.6932
		No	83	92.2		
Student's	Are you having any of your relative/friends nurse?	Yes	7	7	1.9300	0.2564
		No	93	93		
Parent's	Are you having any of your relative/friends nurse?	Yes	18	20	1.8000	0.4022
		No	72	80		
Student's	Are you agreeing for study nursing?	Yes	44	44	1.56000	0.4988
		No	56	56		
Parent's	Are you agreeing for study nursing?	Yes	67	74.4	1.2550	0.4386
		No	23	25.6		

Table (4): Comparison between Students and Parents regarding aspects of nursing image.

Statement	Opinion	Students		Mean	SD	Parents		Mean	SD
		N	%			N	%		
I appreciate those who work in the nursing profession	Strongly agree	0	0	2.9700	1.7145	68	75.6	2.7111	0.54555
	Agree	3	3			4	20.0		
	Disagree	97	97			8	4.4		
When I see a nurse I hope that my son or	Strongly agree	9	9	2.7100	0.62434	90	100	1.0000	0.0000***
	Agree	11	11			0	0		
	Disagree	80	80			0	0		

daughter works like									
Nursing profession humanitarian	Strongly agree	9	9	2.7100	0.62434	90	100	1.0000	0.0000***

	Agree	11	11			0	0		
	Disagree	80	80			0	0		
Work in the field of nursing is fit to a certain class of society	Strongly agree	32	32	2.0800	0.84900	7	7.8	2.7222	0.0000***
	Agree	28	28			11	12.2		
	Disagree	40	40			72	80		
I refuse to work any of my daughter in the field of nursing	Strongly agree	1	1	2.9400	0.27780	0	0	2.9444	0.23034
	Agree	4	4			5	5.6		
	Disagree	95	95			85	94.4		
Nursing profession tired	Strongly agree	17	17	2.6600	0.75505	17	18.9	2.6222	0.78723
	Agree	0	0			0	0		
	Disagree	83	83			73	81.1		
Despite the society of working in the nursing profession	Strongly agree	32	32	2.0800	0.84900	7	7.8	2.7222	0.60015
	Agree	28	28			11	12.2		
	Disagree	40	40			72	80		
Habits in Saudi prevent us from working in the field of nursing	Strongly agree	5	5	2.0800	0.41875	5	5.6	2.0889	0.44075
	Agree	82	82			72	80		
	Disagree	13	13			13	14.4		
Financial benefits for	Strongly agree	4	4	1.9300	0.45416	70	77.8	1.3000	0.60800

workers is small in nursing	Agree	79	79			13	14.4		
	Disagree	7	7			7	7.8		
Education institutions specializing in the rehabilitation of the nursing profession a few	Strongly agree	8	8			1	1.1		
	Agree	17	17	2.6700	0.62044	0	0	2.9778	0.21082
	Disagree	75	75			9	98.9		
The working hours of workers in the nursing in appropriate	Strongly agree	17	17			17	18.9		
	Agree	0	0	2.6600	0.75505	0	0	2.6222	0.78723
	Disagree	83	83			73	73		
I hate my children to work in the field of nursing because of the environment surrounding	Strongly agree	3	3			14	15.6		
	Agree	8	8	2.8600	0.42687	14	15.6	2.5333	0.75252
	Disagree	89	89			62	68.9		
I think in teaching one of my sons nursing	Strongly agree	3	3			3	1.6		
	Agree	93	93	2.0100	0.26572	83	43.5	2.0111	0.28023
	Disagree	4	4			4	2.1		
Seen by many to look down on the nursing profession	Strongly agree	8	8			8	8.9		
	Agree	0	0	2.8400	0.54532	0	0	2.8222	0.57236
	Disagree	92	92			82	91.1		
I hate that my son is dealing with	Strongly agree	5	5			5	5.6		
	Agree	82	82	2.0800	0.41875	72	80	2.0889	0.44075

patients	Disagree	13	13			13	14.4		
I advise always to study nursing	Strongly agree	4	4	2.9200	0.39389	4	4.4	2.9111	0.41447
	Agree	0	0			0	0		
	Disagree	96	96			86	95.6		
The nursing profession in not for Saudis	Strongly agree	3	3	2.8600	0.42687	3	3.3	2.8444	0.44749
Employment opportune in the field of nursing a few	Agree	8	8	1.7900	0.40936	8	8.9	1.1667	0.37477
	Disagree	89	89			79	87.8		
	Strongly agree	21	21			75	83.3		
I hope to see all of the workers in the field of nursing Saudis	Agree	79	79	2.6700	0.21082	15	16.7	2.9778	0.21082
	Disagree	0	0			0	0		
	Strongly agree	8	8			89	98.9		
Nursing profession honest	Agree	17	17	1.2400	0.42923	6	607	2.4667	0.62170
	Disagree	75	75			36	40		
	Strongly agree	76	76			48	53.3		
The presence of large numbers of foreign workers in the nursing profession dangers to society in the long run	Agree	24	24	2.6500	0.65713	0	0	3.0000	0.0000***
	Disagree	0	0			0	0		
	Strongly agree	10	10			90	100		
Should have a plane for the preparation	Agree	30	30	1.7000	0.46057	0	0	2.7889	0.41038
	Strongly agree	70	70			19	21.1		

of national competencies in the field of nursing	Disagree	0	0			71	78.9		
Is not possible to lay of foreign workers in the field of nursing	Strongly agree	3	3	2.8600	0.42687	14	15.6	2.5333	0.75252
	Agree	8	8			14	15.6		
	Disagree	89	89			62	68.8		
Saudi nurse better to deal with patients than foreign nurse	Strongly agree	0	0	2.7600	0.42923	0	0	2.6000	0.49264
	Agree	24	24			36	40		
	Disagree	76	76			54	60		

Table (5): Comparison between Students and Parents opinion regarding the effects of the reluctance of the Saudi youth for the nursing Profession.

Questions	Opinion	Students		Mean	SD	Parents		Mean	SD
		N	%			N	%		
1- Dependence on foreign labor	Strongly agree	7	7	2.4700	0.62692	7	7.8	2.5222	0.64001
	Agree	39	39			29	32.2		
	Disagree	54	54			54	60		
2- Subject to transfer funds out of the country	Strongly agree	17	17	2.4400	0.76963	17	18.9	2.3778	0.78723
	Agree	22	22			22	24.4		
	Disagree	61	61			51	56.7		
3- Loss of human resources of the country of citizenship qualified in	Strongly agree	17	17	2.4400	0.59459	17	18.9	2.3778	0.59459
	Agree	22	22			22	24.4		
	Disagree	61	61			51	56.7		

the field of nursing									
4- Bringing customs contrary to the habits of the Saudi society	Strongly agree	7	7	2.3000	0.59459	7	7.8	2.2222	0.57627
	Agree	56	56			56	62.2		
	Disagree	37	37			27	30		
5- To remain of the mercy of the countries that export labor nursing	Strongly agree	9	9	2.5100	0.6589	9	10	2.4556	0.67310
	Agree	31	31			31	34.4		
	Disagree	60	60			50	55.6		
6- The possibility of foreign workers to leave their work if found better opportune outside the Kingdom	Strongly agree	0	0	2.4800	0.50212	0	0	2.5333	0.50168
	Agree	52	52			42	46.7		
	Disagree	48	48			48	53.3		
7- Bring employment are not eligible effecting the heath level of society	Strongly agree	7	7	2.3000	0.59459	7	7.8	2.2222	0.57627
	Agree	56	56			56	62.2		
	Disagree	37	37			27	30		
8- Weakling of national security	Strongly agree	0	0	2.19000	0.39428	0	0	2.1000	0.30168
	Agree	81	81			81	90		
	Disagree	19	19			9	10		

9- Contributing to the low level of health in the Kingdom	Strongly agree	2	2	2.4100	0.53362	2	2.2	2.3444	0.52277
	Agree	55	55			55	61.1		
	Disagree	43	43			33	36.7		
10- Increase the level of employment among members of the community	Strongly agree	2	2	1.9800	0.14071	2	2.2	1.9778	0.14823
	Agree	98	98			88	97.8		
	Disagree	0	0			0	0		

Table (6): Parents opinion regarding intend to teach female and male children in the field of nursing.

Parent's opinion	Female study		Mean	SD	Male study		Mean	SD
	N	%			N	%		
Yes	11	12.2	1.8778	0.32938	19	16.2	1.8376	0.37040
No	79	87.8			98	83.8		

Table (7): Correlation between family income for both students and parents and study in the field of nursing.

Study nursing	Student income		T-Test	Parents income		T-Test
	Mean	SD	0.0000***	Mean	SD	0.0000***
	2.6768	0.58603		1.3444	0.63884	

*** Highly Significant

Table (8): Comparison of Students and Parents opinion regarding studying in the field of nursing in relation to their age.

Study nursing	Age Grouping							X ²
	Parents			X ²	Students			
	40-45	45-50	Above 50		19-22	22-25	Above 25	

Yes	31	30	6	0.000***	25	9	10	0.000***
No	11	12	0		11	37	8	

***** HIGHLY SIGNIFICANT**

Table (9) Suggestions for nursing image improvement as expressed by students and their parents

Items of improvement	Students suggestions n=100		Parents suggestions n=90	
	No	%	No	%
1-Improve nurses portrayal by media	69	63.89	31	16.49
2- Improve salary and incentives.	57	52.78	53	28.19
3- Educate physicians how to deal with the nurses	26	24.07	22	11.70
4-Nurses training about communication skills especially with patients	12	11.11	31	16.49
5-Continous staff development	62	57.41	86	45.75
6- Improve the services provided to the nurses e.g .health care	16	14.82	22	11.70
7-Empowering nurses by adequate equipment, recourses and advanced technology	20	18.52	33	17.55
8-Establish effective criteria for nurses selections or Improving the interview methods for nurse's selection.	23	21.30	31	16.49
9-Continous follow-up and performance appraisal.	22	20.37	32	17.02
10- Awareness for patients and their relatives about the nurse role.	21	19.44	21	11.17

V. Disc Discussio

Nursing has huge progresses towards becoming professional in recent decades in comparison with previous decades and is produced a scientific base by academic preparing programs for it. Now, it is the time that the nurses should be aware of the images that they draw as professionals for themselves and others. Since, these images are forming during study and interested the way of forming perceptions (image of profession) and the effective factors on it, has not been considered by students till now and since core concepts and the procedural model of data is not made between co concepts (12). Therefore, the purpose of the current study was to explore the impact of perceived public image on turnover intention of students from joining to nursing profession at king Abdul-Aziz University in Jeddah.

The study revealed that the majority of student's age ranged from 22 to 25 years, and there are a statistically significance difference between student's age group. While 8.4% of students from college of medicine female comps with income ranged between 10000-15000 RS and minor of them ranges from 5000 to 10000 RS and there are a statistically significance difference between student's income and type of colleges. These results are supported by (1) who mentioned that two thirds of the participants did not have an original interest in nursing citing medicine as their first choice. They ended up in nursing because they failed to meet one of the admission criteria for the medical school. Added also, developing an interest in nursing as a respectful competitive occupational choice appears to be linked to its gender-related perceptions. Perceptions which have contributed to a societal classification of nursing as low status and dishonorable (13) they found that around two thirds of their subjects haven chosen nursing as it represented a good opportunity for them to work.

The study showed that comparison between the attitude towards the nursing profession between both students and parents. Table (3) recorded not agree for over ninety percent regarding to nursing profession in items; are you having any of your family nurse; are you having any of your relative/friends nurse; and are you agreeing for studying nursing. While two third studied sample agree with one item only which is „are you agreeing for studying nursing?“. These results congruent with the results of (14) they study showed positive changes in the image of nursing as a profession among more than half of the studied subjects. The following will explore the factors affecting that positive change; working conditions, clinical training, relationship with faculty members and relationship with friends regarding aspects of nursing image in items; when I see a nurse I hope that my son or daughter works like; nursing profession humanitarian; work in the field of nursing is fit to a certain class of society and the presence of large numbers of foreign workers in the nursing profession dangers to society in the long run, shows that there were a highly statistically difference between students and their parents. This finding agrees with (15; 16) Saudi women are also slowly becoming employed as doctors, nurses and allied health workers. Nevertheless, Saudi females who choose nursing as a career face many obstacles, primarily based on religious and social norms. Nursing suffers from a poor image in Saudi society, which considers it a job for "maids" or uneducated women. While this finding incongruent with (17) determined Seeking for recognizing duality factor/uniting or according perceived double images. Conceptual domains of bachelor"s degree students about this profession include: the profession"s social status. The nature of nursing knowledge/profession actually/delivering nursing (nursing administering). And the stages of divalent imaging include: ambiguity, event and contrary knowledge and instability, event and valuable knowledge and confidence, accepting and verifying accordant aspect and justifying the contrary aspect (verifying that the images are not accordant) and the presentation of amending propositions (for more accordance of contrary aspect). Regarding the effects of the reluctance of the Saudi youth for the nursing profession. Findings revealed that highest percent for studied sample expressed agreement related to items: increase the level of employment among members of the community and weak of national security. Further the lowest percentage of strongly agreement was expressed by students and their parents were

regarding items: dependence on foreign labor and bringing customs contrary to the habits of the Saudi society. This results congruent with (1) being unacceptable to the mainstream of Islam, Saudi people viewed these foreign female nurses as enjoying religious and moral sexual freedom. Such stereotyping further damaged the image of nurses and discouraged Saudi families from considering nursing as a career for their own daughters. In addition to being predominantly foreign and female, these nurses were expected to assist medical doctors, follow their orders and provide a level of care perceived as menial and unskilled. While commenting on some fifteenth century depictions of nurses, similar images of preNightingale western nurses

Regarding intend to teach female and male children in the field of nursing. Findings revealed that majority of the parents were disagreeing with teaching one of my sons nursing. The se findings supported by (1) who mentioned that In Saudi Arabia, school students do not have any community-based educational experiences¹⁹ that expose them to the occupational choices available to them. They do not have access to school nurses. They are not prepared or trained for any type of voluntary work and they do not even have access to or link with the surrounding community services such as the local health centre, hospital or welfare society. Moreover, under the patriarchal educational system, reading books for school children tend to refer to or use examples of doctors, engineers and pilots who represent highly-regarded male professionals. In contrast, examples of nurses, being predominantly women, and even stories of heroic female nurses in the early Islamic era are often excluded from the taught curricula and most reading materials available for school students particularly the males. This might be attributed to efforts aimed at restricting women's work opportunities in the society. Making nursing a childhood dream was a strategy suggested by some participants who believed that introducing occupations such as nursing to young children should promote relevant awareness and establish baseline interest.

There was highly significant difference between students and their parents' opinion regarding studying in the field of nursing in relation to their age. Also these findings agree with mentioned by (16) Saudi men who choose nursing also face criticism from family and friends. One Saudi male nurse known to the authors related, "My mother refused to tell her friends I am a nurse. If they see me in the hospital, she tells them I am a doctor, as doctors are better than nurses." (However, the difficulty of women in nursing in Saudi Arabia is more problematic than men and needs to be recorded and shared with the global nursing community.

Regarding suggestion to improving nursing image there was highly percentage reported by students in relation to improve nurse's portrayal by media while low percent related to nurses should be training about communication skills especially with patients. On the contrary the parents reported highest percent for item continuous staff development while low percent was reported to awareness for patients and their relatives about the nurse role. These findings agree with stated by (17.et.al) students referred to social status of profession in their words and stated it lower than the nursing real value. e.g when accepting for nursing I want to explain to my grandfather that what nursing is in fact. Saudi Arabian society is divided in its view of the nursing profession. Nursing is not considered a respectable profession for women in Saudi Arabia. In 1991, nursing was ranked last in the list of appropriate occupations for women. Rea sons for this

low ranking included the type of work, inadequate financial rewards and working hours. Working hours are prohibitive for some women as they must fulfill obligations of the wife and mother role (18). These findings supported by (19) explain the high percentage of single female nurse (37.8%) in the study, since Saudi women traditionally marry at a young age. The study authors observed that young Saudis, both male and female, choose careers that offered higher prestige and financial remuneration than nursing. These two research studies demonstrate that the societal perception of female nurses is that of unsuitable marriage partners.

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VI. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study revealed that the majority of student's age ranged from 22 to 25 years, and there are a statistically significance difference between student's age group. While more than two third studied sample agree for studying of nursing and also showed that there were a highly statistically difference between students and their parents as regard to studying of nursing well as there are a statistically significance difference between student's income and type of colleges. Finally, Findings revealed that majority of the parents were disagree with teaching of their sons nursing

VII. Recommendations

- 1- Conducting conference for newly admitted students to orient them about the nursing profession, history of nursing, nursing education programs and different clinical experiences
- 2- Regular visits to secondary school and provision talks of a role model nurse about nursing and role of nurse
- 3- Longitudinal study to examine male nursing students regarding nursing image replicate the abstract as the conclusion.

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